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ABOUT LEXICAL-SEMANTIC WORD GROUPS IN NORTH-WESTERN DIALECTS OF THE AZERBAIJANI LANGUAGE

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О ЛЕКСИКО-СЕМАНТИЧЕСКИХ ГРУППАХ СЛОВ В СЕВЕРО-ЗАПАДНЫХ ДИАЛЕКТАХ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Abstract.

In this article, the lexical-semantic word groups in the dialects of the North-West region were systematically investigated. On the basis of the lexical units in the regional dialects, polysemous words, homonyms, synonyms, and antonyms were studied from a theoretical point of view, and information was provided about the linguistic relations between those word groups.

Changes in meaning, i.e. polysemanticity, are mainly characteristic of nouns, adjectives, and verbs. The shades of meaning of polysemous adjectives used in regional dialects are realized either within word combinations or in the speech situation; it is even possible to come across adjectives in our dialects where the boundaries between meaning relationships are difficult to define.

In addition to homonyms of the same origin formed as a result of the semantic transformation of polysemous words in the vocabulary of North-western dialects, there are a large number of semantically unrelated lexical units of different origins based on random sound matching. Homonyms are classified in different groups according to the fact that they consist of borrowed words or words of Turkic origin, according to their grammatical meaning, lexical-grammatical and mixed homonyms are distinguished from homonyms belonging to the same part of speech.

Absolute and relative synonyms in Northwest dialects were investigated. The morphological structure of the words in the synonymy series is simple, derivative or complex, whether the origin is national or borrowed, is an indicator of the formation of synonyms used in our dialects in different forms.

In Northwest dialects, adjectives, numbers and verbs, and even phraseological units can be used as antonyms. In the lexical composition of regional dialects, it is possible to observe antonyms that differ according to their origin and morphological structure.

Both in the literary language and in the dialect, there are opposite-meaning words that, unlike antonyms, have the same phonetic composition as homonyms and polysemous words. The fact that the same phonetic composition is a member of the polysemantic, homonymous, synonymous and antonymous pair, which is functional in regional dialects as well as in the literary language, reflects the relationship between lexical-semantic categories.

Аннотация.

В данной статье систематически исследованы лексико-семантические группы слов в говорах Северо-Западного региона. На основе лексических единиц региональных диалектов с теоретической точки зрения изучены многозначные слова, омонимы, синонимы и антонимы, а также даны сведения о языковых отношениях между этими группами слов.

Изменения значения, т. е. многозначность, свойственны главным образом существительным, прилагательным и глаголам. Оттенки значения многозначных прилагательных, употребляемых в региональных диалектах, реализуются либо в составе словосочетаний, либо в речевой ситуации; в наших диалектах можно даже встретить прилагательные, в которых границы между смысловыми отношениями определить трудно.

Помимо омонимов одного происхождения, образовавшихся в результате семантической трансформации многозначных слов, в лексике северо-западных говоров имеется большое количество семантически не связанных друг с другом лексических единиц разного происхождения, основанных на случайном сопоставлении звуков. Омонимы классифицируются в разные группы в зависимости от того, состоят ли они из заимствованных слов или слов тюркского происхождения, по грамматическому значению от омонимов, принадлежащих к одной и той же части речи, выделяют лексико-грамматические и смешанные омонимы.

Исследованы абсолютные и относительные синонимы в диалектах Северо-Запада. Морфологическая структура слов в синонимическом ряду простая, производная или сложная, независимо от того, является ли происхождение национальным или заимствованным, является показателем формирования синонимов, употребляемых в наших диалектах в разных формах.

В северо-западных диалектах в качестве антонимов могут использоваться прилагательные, числа и глаголы, и даже фразеологизмы. В лексическом составе региональных диалектов можно наблюдать антонимы, различающиеся по происхождению и морфологической структуре.

Как в литературном языке, так и в диалекте существуют слова противоположного значения, которые, в отличие от антонимов, имеют тот же фонетический состав, что и омонимы, и многозначные слова. Тот факт, что один и тот же фонетический состав входит в многозначную, омонимическую, синонимическую и антонимическую пару, функциональную как в региональных диалектах, так и в литературном языке, отражает соотношение между лексико-семантическими категориями.

Key words: *dialects of the northwestern region, lexical-semantic word groups, polysemous words, mixed homonyms, absolute synonyms, enantiosemy*

Ключевые слова: *диалекты северо-западного региона, лексико-семантические группы слов, многозначные слова, смешанные омонимы, абсолютные синонимы, энантиосемия.*

The lexicon of the dialects of the north-western region of the Azerbaijani language is selected for a number of specific features. As we say northwest dialects, here we mean the dialects of the Sheki, Oguz, Zagatala, Gakh and Balakan regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Polysyllabic words, homonyms, synonyms and antonyms occupy a certain place in the lexical composition of the dialects of the northwestern region of Azerbaijan.

In North-Western dialects, most of the polysemous words consist of nouns, and they are polysemous based on metaphors, metonymy, and synecdoche.

Bebe (Sheki) - 1. baby, child; 2. doll. - *Bəbə öymüzə gələnən sor:a heç rahatdığımız qalmıytdə (- After the baby arrives in our home, we do not find comfort. - Anan gəlincən bəbələrinnən oyniyərsən (Play with your dolls until mommy comes).* The nominative meaning of the word is "baby". The characteristic of baby, first of all, is that it is very small. This sign take on a metaphorical meaning through metaphorical transfer and led to the emergence of the meaning of "doll".

Metonymies differ from metaphors because the transfer of meaning occurs not on the basis of similarity, but on the basis of temporal and spatial relationships. When the transfer of metonymy is related to the place, the polysemantic word includes both the name of the place and the population living temporarily or permanently in that place, that is, its "content". Ex.: oymakh (Sheki, Oguz.) - 1. generation, tribe; 2. hamlet, village; tabin (Zagatala, Qakh, Balakan) - 1. tribe, generation; 2. neighborhood. In north-western dialects, metonymy is mainly formed on the basis of spatial relations [6, p.72].

Sibyl (Zagatala, Balakan) is a multi-meaning word used in the meanings of "corner" and "cornerstone". As H. Hasanov showed, "here the same word expressed the whole or a part of the whole", resulting in a synecdoche [2, p.39]: mujur (Zagatala, Qakh) - 1. one-year-old male goat kid; 2. a goat that goes ahead of the herd (Zagatala). Synecdoche forming from the use of a common word for a particular item is more commonly found in northwestern dialect: sirt - 1. peak (Oguz, Qakh); 2. hill (Sheki, Zagatala, Qakh); 3. uphill (Zagatala); 4. a head or a tall part of anything (Sheki, Oguz).

One of the main parts of speech, the polysemy of an adjective depends on the meaning types of it and the nouns it belongs to, and the relationships of both parts of speech. These relationships lead to the realization of the shades of meaning of adjectives either within a word combination or within a speech situation. In most

cases, adjectives denoting volume, size, and taste are ambiguous within a word combination. From this point of view, the polysemous adjectives used in the north-western dialects can be systematized as follows:

1. Multiple-meaning adjectives with shades of meaning within the word combination: Shidırgı (Sheki) - 1. non-stop, fast (dance); 2. continuous, heavy (rain). This ambiguous word is used in the sense of "non-stop, fast" when connected with the noun dance, and "continuous, strong" when connected with the noun rain.

2. Multiple-meaning adjectives realized in the speech situation. This group of polysemous words includes adjectives that are capable of expressing certain nuances of meaning either literally or figuratively under the influence of different grammatical categories: Hompolov (Zagatala) - 1. big-bellied. - *Hompolov adam ağır yerişər (A big-bellied person walks heavily);* 2. greedy. - *İlyas tamahkar olduğu üçün onu mağazadan qovutdular (Ilyas was kicked out of the store because he was greedy).*

3. Adjectives where the boundaries between meaning relationships are difficult to define: The closeness between the nominative meaning of polysemous words and the derived meanings sometimes reaches such a level that it is not easy to notice the difference between the shades of meaning of the adjectives connected with any noun within a word combination or sentence. Ex.: Otucu (Sheki) - 1. knowledgeable, omniscient; 2. clever, cunning. Jafar is a very cunning child (1, p.383).

Quite a number of polysemous verbs have been recorded in North-Western dialects [3, p.66]. Poralmıx (Sheki - Kishlaq) - 1. to change the state; 2. to deteriorate (of the weather). According to A.G.Alekbarov, "In order to objectively determine the separate meanings of a polysemous verb, first of all, it is necessary to reveal the categorical-semantic content of both the verb and the nouns that make up its configurational scope in interaction". The shades of meaning of the verb *poralmıx* are realized in its relationship with animate and inanimate nouns. So, this polysemous word means "to change the state" when used with specific nouns that denote the human concept in the first sense. *Poralmıx* is associated with inanimate nouns denoting abstract concepts in the second sense.

One of the main parts of speech is the style of adverbs-movement, time, place, quantity, etc. There are different types of meaning. From this point of view, the options included in the structure of ambiguous adverbs have different semantics. Shurullayı (Og.) - 1. in vain; 2. vagabond. - *Şurullayı geyif özün qayutdın (- You left in vain and came back yourself); - O, şurullayının bi-*

ridi (- *He is one of the vagabonds*) (1, p.475). *Shurullayi* is one of the adverbs expressing the manner of movement. But we should also remind that adverbs and adjectives can overlap in terms of different types of meaning, that is, "*cases of crossing or crossing with other parts of speech can also appear*" [3, p.162].

From this point of view, *shurullai*, which is an adverb of manner-action, is a typical example from the lexical-semantic point of view.

So, lexical-semantic word groups form a system and in all cases are related to each other.

Although homonyms have the same sound composition as polysemous words, they express completely different meanings, belong to the same or different parts of speech, and differ in origin.

Homonyms can be grouped into two main groups according to their origin:

1. Homonyms formed when one of the meanings of polysemous words deviates from its meaning and acquires a direct meaning: *Balba I* (Sheki, Oğuz, Zagatala) // *balva I* (Sheki) - the name of an edible wild plant. *Balba II* (Sheki, Zagatala, Qakh) // *balva II* - "a dish prepared from *balva* plant, various herbs, rice, eggs, oil". The semantic process (homonymization) related to the breaking up of ambiguous words and acquiring a completely new, independent meaning or content is manifested on the basis of the above examples: "*plant*" called *balba*, *balva*, and "*food made from that plant*" express concepts that have a certain affinity, and those homonyms confirms the same origin.

2. Lexical homonyms of different origins based on random sound matching: *Hil I* – a necklace worn by women around their necks. *Hil II* (Sheki) -lie, trick. There is no semantic affinity between these homonyms, which are numerous in regional dialects.

The homonyms used in the dialects of the north-western region consist of words of Turkish origin or borrowed words: *Tabun I* (Balakan) - village. *Tabun II* (Qakh) - herd of horses. According to M.Shiraliyev, the word used in the Kazakh language was transferred to the Russian language from the Turkish languages and means "herd of horses" [4, p. 318].

Homonyms, like all borrowed words, regardless of whether they are used in literary language or dialects, are sometimes subject to phonetic and grammatical changes, and sometimes such words do not follow a graphic, grammatical assimilation or change process: *Uruf I* (Sheki) - a moment in a short time frame, minute. *Uruf II* (Sheki) means "soul". *Uruf* is of Arabic origin and one of the homonyms formed due to phonetic phenomena in borrowed words [5, p.113].

Since homonymization refers to the same and different parts of speech, the homonyms used in dialects of the northwestern region are grouped as lexical, lexical-grammatical, and mixed homonyms. Unlike lexical homonyms, lexical-grammatical homonyms belong to two different parts of speech: *Dumba I* (Sheki) - short <man>. *Dumba II* (Sheki) - hill. It is possible to come across mixed homonyms related to at least three parts of speech in the vocabulary of northwestern dialects: *Tap I* (Sheki, Qakh) - crushed (fruit). *Tap II* (Oğuz) – flat. *Tap III* (Qakh) - a small plain in a hilly place.

The origin of the vocabulary of dialects of the North-West region (Turk origin and borrowing), whether they belong to the same or different parts of speech (lexical, lexical-grammatical, mixed), structural types (simple; derivative; compound), semantic division of polysemous words or it is rich in homonyms that differ in terms of their formation as a result of random sound matching.

Synonyms, which are one of the lexical-semantic word groups, are words that differ in phonetic form and close in meaning. Synonyms are divided into two groups: absolute synonyms; relative synonyms. Absolute synonyms express a certain concept both outside and within the text. Only words that are used in a close sense according to the text are relative synonyms: *Pompur* "curly hair" - *sholduman* (Balakan) "his hair is disheveled, his hair is messy" - are synonyms that express a relative meaning in this sense.

Basically, the main parts of speech such as noun, adjective, verb, adverb can form a synonymic row. In the north-western dialects of the Azerbaijani language, the synonymy of nouns is more common than in the literary language. The fact that the words in this line of synonyms are simple in terms of structure, modified or complex, national or borrowed in terms of origin are indicators of the formation of synonyms in different ways.

In the synonymy of verbs, both their lexical meaning types, morphological-grammatical characteristics and their relationship with words from other parts of speech play an important role. The synonyms of *dishamax* "to sharpen toothed cutting tools (saw, sickle, etc.)" - *khartdamax* "to sharpen with a stone" are mainly used in the dialect of Sheki region.

Polysemantic words and homonyms play a role in the creation of synonymous. Ex.: *curumbul* - 1. without clothes; 2. without shell (walnuts, hazelnuts). With the second meaning of the word *curumbul*, the word *cvrikh* can form a synonym: *cvrikh* (Zagatala) "without shell (walnut, hazelnut, chestnut)" - *curumbul* (Oğuz, Qakh) - "without shell (walnuts, hazelnuts)". *Curumbul* is also the name of a "type of plum" in the dialect of Oghuz region, it is used as homonyms with the lexical unit *curumbul* meaning "shellless (nut, hazelnut)": *Curumbul I* (Oğuz) - the name of a type of plum. *Curumbul II* (Oğuz, Qakh) - 1. without clothes; 2. without shell (walnuts, hazelnuts).

In addition, it is also possible to come across synonymous lines in regional dialects with simplified word forms of complex words: *Jirafe* "skinny" - *quirax* "small, small, small" - *leshgi* (Sheki) "lean, thin".

Synonyms formed by cacophemism express any meaning in a vulgar and rude way and sometimes include not one but several members of the line: *Bogmalanmax* "to eat" - *poshelalak* "to eat, to eat often without chewing well" - *lombalamax* (Oğuz) "eating a lot and in a hurry".

The synonyms created in connection with euphemism affect the softening of the meaning and content and the increase of synonyms: *Isdatmax* (Sheki) "to beat, crush (a person)" - *dalashmax* "to fight".

Antonyms from lexical-semantic word groups are also encountered in the dialects of the northwestern region of the Azerbaijani language. Antonyms are words with opposite meanings.

A characteristic feature of antonyms is not only their opposite meaning, but also their expression with different phonetic forms and unrelated root morphemes. For example: words such as *anjari* (Sheki) "beautiful, handsome" and *anjarsiz* (Sheki) "ugly" used in regional dialects cannot be considered as lexical antonyms.

Alacalı (Sheki) "colorful" - *siyato*: (Sheki) "unicolor"; The completeness and incompleteness of the contradiction manifests itself in antonymous combinations such as *alacalı* (Sheki) "colorful" - *aghjavaz* (Sheki) "white".

Antonyms are classified into 3 groups according to their structure: E.g.: from the antonyms used in North-Western dialects, *ulkerdoğan* (Oguz) "beginning of autumn" - *ulkerbatan* (Oguz) "end of autumn" is a complex antonym.

Antonyms also differ in origin. It is also possible to come across antonyms in the vocabulary of North-Western dialects, which differ in their origin and consist of borrowed and Turkish words. *Ertedan* // *ertedan* (Sheki) "early in the morning, early morning, dawn" - (Sheki, Oguz, Zagatala, Qakh) "evening, sunset time". The word "morning" is used in the ancient Turkish written monuments in the phonetic form "ir" meaning "morning, tomorrow".

Since the concepts expressed by the antonyms cover a person's work activity, lifestyle, and spiritual world, it is possible to group them according to the types of meaning:

1. Antonyms expressing concepts related to a person's work activity: *ajgeyin* (Sheki) "unemployed" - *başıdunukh* (Sheki) "head confused, busy".
2. Antonyms such as *curcur* (Qakh) "clear" - *gimil* (Qakh) "blurred" express concepts related to natural phenomena.
3. Antonyms expressing concepts related to time: *imsek* (Zagatala, Balakan) "morning, sunrise time" - *ilkindi* (Sheki, Oguz, Zagatala, Qakh) "evening, sunset time".
4. Antonyms denoting quality: *khircha* // *khirqa* "untidy" - *uzdan* (Zagatala) "clean, tidy".
5. Antonyms denoting situations: *oqalmax* (Zagatala, Qakh) "to recover" - *nachaxlamax* (Zagatala) "to get sick"; *avshatmax* (Qakh) "to break one's heart" - *eyrishmakh* (Qakh) "to flatter".

One or both of the words forming antonym pairs can be homonyms: *Ornach* (Qakh) "tall" - *ganda* (Qakh, Balakan) "short". The word *ganda*, which means "short" and is used in the dialects of Gakh and Balakan districts, is an antonym equivalent of the lexical unit *ornach* meaning "tall" and is also a homonym. *Ganda I* (Guba, Derbent, Khachmaz) "old buffalo. *Ganda II* (Davachi) "where".

All antonym lines must be in the same pattern from a grammatical point of view. However, there are

words in our language that are considered common words for several parts of speech. Those words having the same phonetic form and lexical meaning are used both as nouns and adverbs or as both numbers and adverbs. In order to determine which part of speech these words belong to, it is important to take into account the object or action they define, and their position in the sentence. The following antonym pairs in regional dialects differ from the main parts of speech in that they belong to the noun and adverb: *Obash* (Sheki, Zagatala) "from dawn, early" - *ilkindi* (Sheki, Oguz, Zagatala, Qakh) "evening, sunset" time".

Compared to the main parts of speech such as nouns, verbs, and adverbs, in North-western dialects, antonym pairs expressed by adjectives are dominant in terms of quantity: *dishdeme* (Sheki) "unsweetened" - *salma* (Sheki) "sweet"; *zolatay* (Qakh, Balakan) "big, huge" - *carcur* (Balakan) "small".

At the same time, antonym pairs consisting of verbs and constituents of phraseological combinations are also interesting. *Oqalmax* (Zagatala, Qakh) "to recover" - *nachaxlamakh* (Zagatala) "to get sick", *mariz tuşk* (Qakh) "to be an enemy" - *mayil durmak* (Qakh) "to take sides".

In contrast to antonyms in regional dialects, opposite words with the same phonetic composition enantiosemy are found: *Düşünüşmak* (Sheki) "to contradict each other"; It is enantiosemy in the meaning of "to match". Such enantiosems used in the literary language and dialects of Azerbaijan are a manifestation of the relations between synonyms - homonyms - antonyms, which are word groups of form and content within the same system, regardless of whether they are studied as an antonymic or homonymic event.

References

1. *Azərbaycan dilinin dialektoloji lüğəti* // Dialectological dictionary of the Azerbaijani language. – Baku: East-West, 2007, – 568 p.
2. *Həsənov H.Ə. Müasir Azərbaycan dilinin leksikası* // Hasanov H.A. Lexicon of the modern Azerbaijani language. – Baku: Education, – 1987, – 308 p.
3. *Müasir Azərbaycan dilinin semasiologiyası (oçerklər)* // Semasiology of the modern Azerbaijani language. – Baku: Science, – 1985, – 244 p.
4. *Şirəliyev, M. Azərbaycan dialektologiyasının əsasları* // Shiraliyev, M. Basics of Azerbaijani dialectology. – Baku: East-West, – 2008. – 416 p.
5. *Гасанов, К.М. Омонимы в диалектах азербайджанского языка* // – Баку: Вопросы диалектологии тюркских языков. Издательство Академии наук Азербайджанской ССР Баку, – т. 4. – 1966. – с. 112-116.
6. *Sadigova, K.R. Multiple words formed on basis of metaphoric al expression in the northwestern dialects of the Azerbaijani language* // – Пенза: European research: Сборник статей XXIII Международной научно-практической конференции. МЦНС «Наука и Просвещение», – 2019, – с.69-73.